

EXISTENCE AND CONTINUOUS DEPENDENCE RESULTS FOR VOLTERRA-FREDHOLM INCLUSION

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Abstract. The solvability of a state-dependent Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential inclusion (V-FIDI) with a nonlocal condition is explored, along with the uniqueness and existence of its solutions. We first prove the uniqueness and existence properties of the solution under certain assumptions about the given data. Lastly, a sample that highlights the primary finding is provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since many mathematical models are used to formulate various phenomena, such as mechanics, physics, chemical kinetics, astronomy, biology, economics, potential theory, and electrostatics, which are modelled using integro-differential equations, differential equations and integral equations have recently become extremely important in several branches of science and engineering [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20, 25, 28].

In mathematical physics, nonlocal issues are those in which the values of the desired function at different locations along the boundary are connected, in contrast to typical boundary value requirements. In the differential and integral equations with diverging arguments found in the present literature, the argument's deviation often only affects the time itself, as seen in [1, 2, 18, 19, 21, 22, 24]. Alternatively, there is another instance, both in theory and in practise, where the deviating arguments rely on the time φ as well as the state variable Φ . Recently, a number of papers have been published, for instance [3, 4, 5, 26, 29], that focus on these differential equations.

The differential equation's unique solution was examined in the earliest studies of this family of functional equations with self-reference, by Eder [6].

$$\Psi'(\varphi) = \Psi(\Psi(\varphi)), \quad \Psi(0) = \Psi_0, \quad \varphi \in \eta \subset \mathbb{R}$$

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Wang [27] investigated the equation's maximal strong solution as well as its strong solution.

$$\Psi'(\varphi) = B(\Psi(\Psi(\varphi)))$$

where $B : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is monotone and continuous and $B(0) = 0$.

Buica [3] investigated the functional differential equation's continuous dependence and existence of solutions on Ψ_0 :

$$\Psi'(\varphi) = B(\varphi, \Psi(\Psi(\varphi))), \quad \Psi(\varphi_0) = \Psi_0, \quad \varphi \in [a, d]$$

where $\varphi_0, \Psi_0 \in [a, d]$ and $B \in C([a, d], [a, d])$.

The V-FIDI with self-dependence on a nonlinear operator is examined in this work.

$$\frac{d\Phi}{d\varphi} \in \Psi \left(\varphi, \int_0^{\Omega(\varphi)} \Phi \xi(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))d\hbar, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))d\hbar \right) \text{ a.e. } \varphi \in (0, \eta] \quad (1.1)$$

$$\Phi(0) + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) = \Phi_0, \quad \Delta_\gamma > 0, \quad \rho_\gamma \in (0, \eta). \quad (1.2)$$

We investigate the existence and uniqueness of the solution $\Phi \in AC[0, \eta]$ and demonstrate the continuous dependence on Φ_0 and ξ .

2. PRELIMINARIES

Take into account these presumptions:

- (a) $\Psi(\varphi, \Phi)$ be nonempty, closed and convex $\forall(\varphi, \Phi) \in [0, \eta] \times \mathbb{R}$.
- (b) $\Psi(\varphi, \Phi)$ be measurable in $\varphi \in [0, \eta]$ for every $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (c) $\Psi(\varphi, \Phi)$ be semi upper continuous in Φ for every $\varphi \in [0, \eta]$.
- (d) There exist a measurable bounded function $c : [0, \eta] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and constant $\Upsilon > 0$, such that

$$\|\Psi(\varphi, \Phi)\| = \sup\{|\mathfrak{S}| : \mathfrak{S} \in \Psi(\varphi, \Phi)\} \leq |c(\varphi)| + \Upsilon|\Phi|, \quad |c(\varphi)| \leq M$$

We may infer that there exists a $\mathfrak{S} \in \Psi(\varphi, \Phi)$ such that the following is met based on the assumptions (a)–(d):

(A1). $\mathfrak{S} : [0, \eta] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ fulfils the Caratheodory requirement:

- For each $\varphi \in [0, \eta]$, $\mathfrak{S}(\varphi, \cdot, \cdot)$ is continuous;
- For each $\theta, \theta_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $\mathfrak{S}(\cdot, \theta, \theta_1)$ is measurable;
- There exist a measurable bounded function $c(\varphi)$ and a constant $\Upsilon, \Upsilon_1 > 0$, such that

$$|\mathfrak{S}(\varphi, \theta, \theta_1)| \leq |c(\varphi)| + \Upsilon|\theta| + \Upsilon_1|\theta_1|, \quad |c(\varphi)| \leq M,$$

and the functional $\mathfrak{S}$ satisfies the Volterra-Fredholm equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d\Phi}{d\wp} \tag{2.1} \\ = & \mathfrak{S} \left(\wp, \int_0^{\Omega(\wp)} \Phi \xi(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))d\hbar, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))d\hbar \right) \text{ a.e. } \wp \in (0, \eta], \end{aligned}$$

(A2). $\xi, \vartheta : [0, \eta] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ fulfils the Caratheodory requirement:

- For each $\wp \in [0, \eta], \xi(\wp, \cdot), \vartheta(\wp, \cdot)$ be continuous;
- For each $\wp \in \mathbb{R}, \xi(\cdot, \Phi), \vartheta(\cdot, \Phi)$ be measurable;
- $|\xi(\wp, \Phi)| \leq 1, |\vartheta(\wp, \Phi)| \leq 1$.

(A3). $\Omega : [0, \eta] \rightarrow [0, \eta]$ is nondecreasing continuous, $\Omega(\wp) \leq \wp, \wp \in [0, \eta]$.

(A4). $(1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_\gamma) (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta < 1$.

Remark 2.1. We may infer from (a) and (1.1) that each solution to (1.1) also solves (2.1).

Lemma 2.2. *If (A1)-(A4) satisfies, then the system (1.1)-(1.2) and the equation*

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(\wp) = & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \\ & \times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \tag{2.2} \\ & + \int_0^\wp \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \text{ for } \wp \in [0, \eta] \end{aligned}$$

are equivalent.

Proof. Let the solution of the system (1.1)-(1.2) exists. Integrating (2.1) from 0 to $\wp$, we have

$$\Phi(\wp) = \Phi(0) + \int_0^\wp \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \tag{2.3}$$

Using (1.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) \\ = & \Phi(0) \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \end{aligned}$$

By $\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) = \Phi_0 - \Phi(0)$, we get

$$\Phi_0 - \Phi(0) = \Phi(0) \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar,$$

which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(0) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \tag{2.4} \\ &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \end{aligned}$$

Using (2.3)-(2.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(\varphi) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \\ &\left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ &+ \int_0^{\varphi} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar. \end{aligned}$$

Now, assume that $\Phi \in C[0, \eta]$ is a solution of (2.2). Now differentiate (2.2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\Phi}{d\varphi} &= \frac{d}{d\varphi} \left\{ \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \right. \\ &\left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ &+ \int_0^{\varphi} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \left. \right\} \\ &= \mathfrak{S} \left(\varphi, \int_0^{\Omega(\varphi)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right). \end{aligned}$$

From (2.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(\rho_\gamma) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \\ &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ &+ \int_0^{\rho_\gamma} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar, \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(0) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \\ &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right], \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \\ &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ &+ \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar. \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

From (2.5) and (2.6), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(0) + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \right) \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ &+ \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\Phi(0) + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \Phi(\Omega(\rho_\gamma)) = \Phi_0$$

The proof is finished now.

3. RESULTS

Hare, we prove that there is at least one solution to system (1.1)-(1.2) using Schauder’s argument.

Theorem 3.1. *Let the hypotheses (A1)-(A4) be hold, then the system (1.1)-(1.2) has at least one solution $\Phi \in AC[0, \eta]$.*

Proof. We first establish P_L , create the operator A related to Eq. (2.2) by

$$\begin{aligned}
 A\Phi(\wp) &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \\
 &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\
 &+ \int_0^{\wp} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now $P_L = \{\Phi \in C[0, \eta] : |\Phi(\wp) - \Phi(\hbar)| \leq L|\wp - \hbar|, \forall \wp, \hbar \in [0, \eta]\}$, where

$$L = \frac{(\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) |\Phi_0| + \left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_{\gamma}\right) M}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_{\gamma}\right) - \left(1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}\right) (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta}$$

Hence, we get for $\Phi \in P$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |A\Phi(\wp)| &= \left| \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \right. \\
 &\times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\
 &+ \left. \int_0^{\wp} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) d\hbar \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[\left| \Phi_0 \right| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \right. \\
 &\times \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \left. \right] \\
 &+ \int_0^{\wp} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar,
 \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |A\Phi(\varphi)| \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} (|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| \right. \\
 & \left. + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right|) d\hbar \right] \\
 & + \int_0^{\wp} \left(|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| \right) d\hbar \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} (|c(\hbar)| \right. \\
 & \left. + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \right. \\
 & \left. + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)| \right) d\hbar \\
 & + \int_0^{\wp} (|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \\
 & + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)|) d\hbar. \tag{3.1} \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} (|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon L \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \right. \\
 & \left. + \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)|) d\hbar \right] \\
 & + \int_0^{\wp} (|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon L \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \\
 & + \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)|) d\hbar \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} |\Phi_0| + \frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta |\Phi(0)|) \\
 & + \eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta |\Phi(0)| \\
 = & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} |\Phi_0| + \left(\frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_{\gamma}} + 1 \right) (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta |\Phi(0)|).
 \end{aligned}$$

But

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Phi(0)| \\
 &= \left| \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Phi(0)| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} (|c(\hbar)| \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)| \right) d\hbar \Big] \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left(|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon L \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon |\Phi(0)| \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta + \Upsilon_1 |\Phi(0)| \right) d\hbar \right] \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left[|\Phi_0| + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta |\Phi(0)|) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$|\Phi(0)| \leq \frac{|\Phi_0| + (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) L \eta^2) \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}\right) - (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \eta \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}} \tag{3.2}$$

From (3.1)-(3.2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |A\Phi(\wp)| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} |\Phi_0| + \left(\frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} + 1 \right) \\
 & \quad \times (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta|\Phi(0)|) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} |\Phi_0| + \left(\frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} + 1 \right) \\
 & \quad \times \left(\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta \frac{|\Phi_0| + (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta^2) \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma\right) - (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} \right) \\
 & = \frac{|\Phi_0| + (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta^2) \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma\right) - (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} + L\eta.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, let $\wp_1, \wp_2 \in (0, \eta]$ such that $|\wp_2 - \wp_1| < \delta$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |A\Phi(\wp_2) - A\Phi(\wp_1)| \\
 & \leq \int_{\wp_1}^{\wp_2} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \\
 & \leq \int_{\wp_1}^{\wp_2} \left(|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon|\Phi(0)| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \Upsilon_1 \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))d\theta - \Phi(0) \right| + \Upsilon_1|\Phi(0)| \right) d\hbar \tag{3.3} \\
 & \leq \int_{\wp_1}^{\wp_2} \left(|c(\hbar)| + \Upsilon L \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))|d\theta + \Upsilon|\Phi(0)| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^\eta |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))|d\theta + \Upsilon_1|\Phi(0)| \right) d\hbar \\
 & \leq (\wp_2 - \wp_1) M + (\wp_2 - \wp_1) (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta + (\wp_2 - \wp_1) (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)|\Phi(0)| \\
 & = (\wp_2 - \wp_1) (M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)|\Phi(0)|).
 \end{aligned}$$

From (3.2)-(3.3), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |A\Phi(\wp_2) - A\Phi(\wp_1)| \\
 & \leq (\wp_2 - \wp_1) (M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta \\
 & \quad + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) \left(\frac{|\Phi_0| + (\eta M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta^2) \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma\right) - (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_\gamma} \right))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq (\wp_2 - \wp_1) \frac{(\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1) |\Phi_0| + \left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_\gamma\right) (M + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)L\eta)}{\left(1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_\gamma\right) - (\Upsilon + \Upsilon_1)\eta \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\mathcal{K}} \Delta_\gamma} = (\wp_2 - \wp_1) L.$$

This shows that $A : P_L \rightarrow P_L$; the class of functions $\{A\Phi\}$ is uniformly equi-continuous and bounded in P_L .

Let $\Phi_n \in P_L, \Phi_n \rightarrow \Phi (n \rightarrow \infty)$, then from hypotheses **(A1)**-**(A2)**, we get $\mathfrak{S}(\wp, \Phi_n(\wp), \Phi_n(\wp)) \rightarrow \mathfrak{S}(\wp, \Phi(\wp), \Phi(\wp)), \xi(\wp, \Phi_n(\wp)) \rightarrow \xi(\wp, \Phi(\wp))$ and $\vartheta(\wp, \Phi_n(\wp)) \rightarrow \vartheta(\wp, \Phi(\wp))$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Also

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A\Phi_n(\wp) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \times \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta \right) \, d\hbar \Big] \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^\wp \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta \right) \, d\hbar \right). \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \\ & \leq \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \\ & \leq L \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) - \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| \, d\theta + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \\ & \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{\epsilon}{2} = \epsilon. \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \\
 & \leq \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \\
 & \quad + \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) \, d\theta \right| \tag{3.6} \\
 & \leq L \int_0^\eta |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) - \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| \, d\theta + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \\
 & \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{\epsilon}{2} = \epsilon.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using (3.4), (3.5) and (3.6) and The dominated convergence theorem of Lebesgue [23], we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A\Phi_n(\varphi) \\
 & = \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma} \\
 & \quad \times \left[\Phi_0 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta \right) \, d\hbar \right] \\
 & \quad + \int_0^\varphi \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi_n \xi(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta, \int_0^\eta \Phi_n \vartheta(\theta, \Phi_n(\theta)) \, d\theta \right) \, d\hbar \\
 & = A\Phi(\varphi).
 \end{aligned}$$

Then $A\Phi_n \rightarrow A\Phi$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the operator A is continuous.

Therefore, by the Schauder's theorem [23], for Eq. (2.2), there exists at least one solution $\Phi \in C[0, \eta]$; consequently, for the system (1.1)-(1.2), there exists at least one solution $\Phi \in AC[0, \eta]$.

Remark 3.2. We may infer from these hypotheses that there is a function $\mathfrak{S} \in \Psi(\varphi, \Phi, \Lambda)$ such that,

(B1). $\mathfrak{S} : [0, \eta] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is measurable in φ for any $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}$ and satisfies the Lipschitz condition

$$|\mathfrak{S}(\varphi, \Phi, \Lambda) - \mathfrak{S}(\varphi, M, N)| \leq \Upsilon|\Phi - M| + \Upsilon^*|\Lambda - N|.$$

(B2). $\xi, \vartheta : [0, \eta] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be measurable in $\varphi, \forall \Phi \in \mathbb{R}$ and satisfies the Lipschitz conditions

$$|\xi(\varphi, \Phi) - \xi(\varphi, q)| \leq \Upsilon_1|\Phi - q|, \quad |\vartheta(\varphi, \Phi) - \vartheta(\varphi, q)| \leq \Upsilon_2|\Phi - q|$$

(B3).

$$\left(\frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \right) < 1.$$

Theorem 3.3. *If (B1)-(B3) hold, then the solution of system (1.1)-(1.2) is unique.*

Proof. Let ϖ, Φ be two the solutions of system (1.1)-(1.2). Then

$$\begin{aligned} & |\varpi(\wp) - \Phi(\wp)| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \left(\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\wp, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. - \mathfrak{S} \left(\wp, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \right) \\ & \quad + \int_0^{\wp} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \end{aligned}$$

hence

$$\begin{aligned} & |\varpi(\wp) - \Phi(\wp)| \\ & \leq \frac{\Upsilon}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\ & \quad + \frac{\Upsilon^*}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\ & \quad + \Upsilon \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\ & \quad + \Upsilon^* \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar. \end{aligned}$$

Then, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\varpi(\wp) - \Phi(\wp)| \\
 \leq & \frac{\Upsilon}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \frac{\Upsilon}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \frac{\Upsilon^*}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \frac{\Upsilon^*}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \varpi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \int_0^{\wp} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \varpi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar
 \end{aligned}$$

which diminishes to

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\varpi(\wp) - \Phi(\wp)| \\
 \leq & \frac{\Upsilon L}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) - \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \right) \\
 & + \frac{\Upsilon^* L}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) - \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \right) \\
 & + \Upsilon L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) - \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \\
 & + \Upsilon^* L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \varpi(\theta)) - \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon^* \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\varpi(\wp) - \Phi(\wp)| \\
 & \leq \frac{\Upsilon L}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\Upsilon_1 \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\Omega(h)} |\varpi(\theta) - \Phi(\theta)| d\theta dh + \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \right) \\
 & \quad + \frac{\Upsilon^* L}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\Upsilon_2 \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\eta} |\varpi(\theta) - \Phi(\theta)| d\theta dh + \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \right) \\
 & \quad + \Upsilon \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\Omega(h)} |\varpi(\theta) - \Phi(\theta)| d\theta dh + \Upsilon \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \\
 & \quad + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2 L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\eta} |\varpi(\theta) - \Phi(\theta)| d\theta dh + \Upsilon^* \eta \|\varpi - \Phi\| \\
 & \leq \frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} (\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 L \eta^2 + \Upsilon \eta) \|\varpi - \Phi\| + (\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 L \eta^2 + \Upsilon \eta) \|\varpi - \Phi\| \\
 & \quad + \frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} (\Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2 L \eta^2 + \Upsilon^* \eta) \|\varpi - \Phi\| + (\Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2 L \eta^2 + \Upsilon^* \eta) \|\varpi - \Phi\| \\
 & = \frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \|\varpi - \Phi\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\left(1 - \left(\frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \right) \right) \|\varpi - \Phi\| \leq 0.$$

Since

$$\frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) < 1,$$

which implies $\Phi(\wp) = \varpi(\wp)$ and the solution of the system (1.1)-(1.2) is unique.

Theorem 3.4. *Let (A4), (B1)-(B3) hold, then the solution of the system (1.1)-(1.2) depends continuously on Φ_0 .*

Proof. Let Φ^* be a solution of the integral equation

$$\begin{aligned} & \Phi(\varrho) \\ = & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \\ & \times \left[\Phi_0^* - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar \right] \\ & + \int_0^{\varrho} \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) d\hbar, \end{aligned}$$

such that $|\Phi_0 - \Phi_0^*| < \delta$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Phi(\varrho) - \Phi^*(\varrho)| \\ \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} |\Phi_0 - \Phi_0^*| + \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \\ & \times \left(\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\varrho, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. - \mathfrak{S} \left(\varrho, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \right) \\ & + \int_0^{\varrho} \left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right. \\ & \left. - \mathfrak{S} \left(\hbar, \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right) \right| d\hbar \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Phi(\varrho) - \Phi^*(\varrho)| \\ \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \delta \\ & + \Upsilon \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\ & + \Upsilon^* \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \left| \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\eta} \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \Upsilon \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Phi(\varphi) - \Phi^*(\varphi)| \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \delta \\
 & + \Upsilon \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \left| \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^{\Omega(h)} \Phi^* \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar \\
 & + \Upsilon^* \int_0^\varphi \left| \int_0^\eta \Phi \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta - \int_0^\eta \Phi^* \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta)) d\theta \right| d\hbar
 \end{aligned}$$

which diminishes to

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Phi(\varphi) - \Phi^*(\varphi)| \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \delta \\
 & + \Upsilon L \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma} \sum_{\gamma=1}^\Theta \Delta_\gamma \left(\int_0^{\Omega(\rho_\gamma)} \int_0^{\Omega(h)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) - \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ \Upsilon^* L \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) - \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \right) \\
 &+ \Upsilon L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\xi(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) - \xi(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \\
 &+ \Upsilon^* L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\eta} |\vartheta(\theta, \Phi(\theta)) - \vartheta(\theta, \Phi^*(\theta))| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon^* \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\Phi(\wp) - \Phi^*(\wp)| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \delta \\
 &+ \Upsilon L \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\Upsilon_1 \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\Phi(\theta) - \Phi^*(\theta)| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \right) \\
 &+ \Upsilon^* L \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma} \left(\Upsilon_2 \int_0^{\Omega(\rho_{\gamma})} \int_0^{\eta} |\Phi(\theta) - \Phi^*(\theta)| d\theta d\hbar + \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \right) \\
 &+ \Upsilon \Upsilon_1 L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\Omega(\hbar)} |\Phi(\theta) - \Phi^*(\theta)| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \\
 &+ \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2 L \int_0^{\wp} \int_0^{\eta} |\Phi(\theta) - \Phi^*(\theta)| d\theta d\hbar + \Upsilon^* \eta \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \\
 &\leq \frac{\delta}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}} + \frac{\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \\
 &+ ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \\
 &= \frac{\delta}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}} + \frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \|\Phi - \Phi^*\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\|\Phi - \Phi^*\| \leq \frac{\frac{\delta}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^K \Delta_{\gamma}}}{1 - \left(\frac{1 + 2 \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \Delta_{\gamma}} ((\Upsilon \Upsilon_1 + \Upsilon^* \Upsilon_2) L \eta^2 + (\Upsilon + \Upsilon^*) \eta) \right)} = \epsilon.$$

Then the solution of the system (1.1)-(1.2) depends continuously on Φ_0 .

4. APPLICATIONS

Example 1. Consider the V-FIDE

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\Phi}{d\wp} &= \frac{1}{3}\wp^3 + \frac{1}{\wp^2 + 5} \int_0^{\beta\wp} \frac{\Phi \cos^2 \Phi}{1 + e^{\Phi(\hbar)}} d\hbar \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\wp + 16}} \int_0^1 \frac{\Phi \sin^2(\Phi)}{1 + \hbar^2} d\hbar, \quad \wp, \beta \in (0, 1], \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

$$\Phi(0) + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\gamma^4} \Phi \left(\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \right) = 1 \tag{4.2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Phi(\wp) \\ &= \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \gamma^4} \left[1 - \sum_{\gamma=1}^{\Theta} \gamma^6 \int_0^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{1}{3}s^3 + \frac{1}{s^2 + 5} \int_0^{\beta s} \frac{\Phi \cos^2 \Phi}{1 + e^{\Phi(\hbar)}} d\hbar + \frac{1}{\sqrt{s + 16}} \int_0^1 \frac{\Phi \sin^2(\Phi)}{1 + \hbar^2} d\hbar \right) ds \Big] \\ &\quad + \int_0^{\wp} \left(\frac{1}{3}s^3 + \frac{1}{s^2 + 5} \int_0^{\beta s} \frac{\Phi \cos^2 \Phi}{1 + e^{\Phi(\hbar)}} d\hbar + \frac{1}{\sqrt{s + 16}} \int_0^1 \frac{\Phi \sin^2(\Phi)}{1 + \hbar^2} d\hbar \right) ds. \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

Set

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathfrak{S} \left(\wp, \int_0^{\Omega(\wp)} \Phi \xi(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar)) d\hbar, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar)) d\hbar \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{3}\wp^3 + \frac{1}{\wp^2 + 5} \int_0^{\beta\wp} \frac{\Phi \cos^2 \Phi}{1 + e^{\Phi(\hbar)}} d\hbar + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\wp + 16}} \int_0^1 \frac{\Phi \sin^2(\Phi)}{1 + \hbar^2} d\hbar. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\left| \mathfrak{S} \left(\wp, \int_0^{\Omega(\wp)} \Phi \xi(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar)) d\hbar, \int_0^{\eta} \Phi \vartheta(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar)) d\hbar \right) \right| \leq \frac{\wp^3}{3} + \frac{\Phi}{5} + \frac{\Phi}{4},$$

and also

$$|\xi(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))| \leq 1, \quad |\vartheta(\hbar, \Phi(\hbar))| \leq 1.$$

We can see that the hypotheses **(A1)**-**(A4)** of Theorem 3.1 are hold with $|c(\wp)| = \left| \frac{1}{3}\wp^3 \right| \leq \frac{1}{3}$ is measurable bounded, $\Upsilon = \frac{1}{5}$, $\Upsilon^* = \frac{1}{4}$, $L = \left(1 + 2\frac{\pi^4}{1035} \right) \left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{4} \right) \simeq 0.5347$ and the series $\sum_{\gamma=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\gamma^4}$ is convergent. Then, by applying to Theorem 3.1, the given system (4.1)-(4.2) has a solution given by (4.3).

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